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The Effects of Storage Conditions on the eDNA Recovery rate of Salmon Pathogens.

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Abstract

Environmental DNA, eDNA, is considered today as an essential tool for the efficient detection of pathogens in aquatic environments, providing major benefits for monitoring fish health and controlling diseases in aquaculture. This experiment tests and analyzes the effects of different storage conditions on the eDNA recovery rates of two key salmon pathogens: *Yersinia ruckeri*, (*Y.ruc*) and *Aeromonas salmonicida*, (*A.sal*). These pathogens are among the common ones found in aquatic environments and are responsible for enteric redmouth disease and furunculosis, respectively. Moreover, they have significant impacts on salmon populations and aquaculture operations.

The main goals of this research were to evaluate how different storage temperatures, preservation solutions, and time intervals between filtration and testing the eDNA integrity affect the recovery rates of these two pathogens. *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* were grown and cultured in their respective media in the laboratory. After undergoing filtration, a set of the filter papers containing the different concentrations of the pathogens underwent extraction followed by a quantitative Polymerase Chain (qPCR) and the C_q values obtained are considered as the reference value. The other filter papers were subjected to different storage conditions, including temperatures of 20°C (room temperature of the laboratory) and -20°C, preservation with 80% ethanol and time intervals of 1 day, 3 days, 7 days, 10 days and 14 days for *Yersinia* and only 7 days, 10 days and 14 days for *Aeromonas*. This difference in time interval was due to a contamination problem when growing *A.sal*. After the time interval, eDNA was extracted using established protocols and quantified using qPCR. They are then compared to the reference value and their respective standard series values to evaluate the impact of these variables on eDNA recovery.

After experimentation, results showed that the lower storage temperature greatly improved eDNA stability and recovery rates for *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas*. Preservation with ethanol also enhanced eDNA integrity, particularly for samples stored at lower temperatures. The study found that the time between sample filtration and processing is also a major factor, with significant eDNA degradation occurring in unpreserved samples stored at room temperature for more than 24 hours. These findings provide important information concerning the optimal storage conditions for eDNA samples, which can increase the efficiency and reliability of eDNA-based pathogen detection techniques. By testing and studying the best techniques and processes for sample preservation, this research supports the effective monitoring and control of fish health in both natural and aquaculture environments.

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List of Abbreviation

eDNA	Environmental DNA
Yersinia ruckeri	Y.ruc
Aeromonas salmonicida	A.sal
bp	Base pairs
CFU	Colony forming units
Cq	Quantification cycle in which a fluorescence signal exceeds a baseline threshold value in qPCR.
dNTP	Nucleoside triphosphate: DNA building block containing DNA backbone structure and a nucleic acid; dATP, dTTP, dGTP and dCTP.
NTC	No template control: sample consisting of e.g. water to test reaction components for a signal.
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction.
qPCR	Quantitative / real-time polymerase chain reaction; used to amplify, detect and quantify DNA.
Rpm	Rounds per minute; specification of rotational shaking and centrifugation speed.

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1. Introduction

Today, environmental DNA (eDNA) plays a big role in the monitoring and conservation of our environment and aquatic ecology. eDNA is the genetic material obtained directly from environmental samples such as soil, water, or air, without the need for capturing the organisms themselves (Giribet *et al.*, 2018). It is an essential tool for the detection of a variety of organisms, from microorganisms to large animals, based on the DNA they leave behind in their respective environments. eDNA is essential in aquatic environments because the traditional methods of monitoring species and pathogens are often labor-intensive, invasive, and time-consuming (Amarasiri *et al.*, 2021).

The use of eDNA has positively changed the sector of aquatic ecology by enabling a non-invasive method to monitor and control biodiversity, detect invasive species, and investigate ecosystem health. This has proven to be very efficient and accurate, enabling the detection of rare species that might normally go unnoticed using conventional techniques (Duarte *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, eDNA has important implications for pathogen detection, as it enables the identification of disease-causing organisms in water bodies, which is essential for monitoring the health of aquatic organisms, including economically important species such as salmon.

1.1 Importance of aquaculture

Today, aquaculture is an essential factor when addressing the exponential increase in demand for seafood and ensuring global food security. With fish stocks facing depletion due to overfishing and environmental challenges, aquaculture seems to be a sustainable solution to meet the growing demand. It provides a controlled environment for the cultivation of various aquatic species, contributing significantly to the diversification of diets and the reduction of pressure on natural ecosystems (Timi *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, aquaculture promotes economic development by creating employment opportunities and supporting coastal and rural communities. Aquaculture can also help alleviate poverty, enhance proper nutrition, and contribute to overcoming the impacts of climate change. As a result, governments and international organisations such as WHO (World Health Organisation), WFP (World Food Program) increasingly recognize and invest in the development of responsible and sustainable aquaculture practices to secure the future of global food production (Norman *et al.*, 2019).

1.2 Importance of eDNA in monitoring aquatic pathogens

The detection of pathogens in aquatic environments is essential for preserving the health of fish populations and the sustainability of aquaculture. Traditional pathogen detection techniques often involve the capture of fish, followed by laboratory analysis to identify the presence of specific pathogens. These methods can be stressful for the fish, potentially spreading diseases during handling, are time-consuming and are also resource intensive. In contrast, eDNA offers a non-invasive alternative that can provide rapid and efficient detection of pathogens from water samples and without disturbing the fish and its habitat (Thomsen *et al.*, 2015).

Moreover, eDNA sampling can cover large and multiple different areas relatively quickly and inexpensively. This scalability makes it possible to conduct extensive experiments to monitor pathogen presence and distribution across different water bodies, providing a comprehensive understanding of pathogen dynamics and risks. This method also supports studies to track changes in pathogen changes over time, contributing to the development of effective disease management strategies in aquaculture (Goldberg *et al.*, 2016).

1.3 Aquatic pathogens affecting salmon

The ability to detect pathogens using eDNA is very important for the aquaculture of the Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) which is very prominent and growing daily. They are a vital resource for both commercial aquaculture of *Salmo salar* and other salmon species, contributing significantly to global food security and local economies (Feist *et al.*, 2019). Salmon are exposed and affected by a range of bacterial, viral, and parasitic pathogens, which can cause serious economic losses and threaten wild populations.

Among these pathogens, *Yersinia ruckeri* and *Aeromonas salmonicida* are of particular concern and are the most common ones affecting salmon. The two Gram negative bacteria have consequent impact on both farmed and wild fish populations. *Yersinia* is one of the causes for the development of enteric redmouth disease (ERM) among salmonids (Gokhlesh *et al.*, 2015). On the other hand, *Aeromonas* species, including *Aeromonas salmonicida*, contribute to motile *Aeromonas* septicemia (MAS) and furunculosis in fish species. These two pathogens have serious impacts on the economy because they contribute to mass mortality and decrease in productivity in the fish sector (De Silva *et al.*, 2022).

Table 1: Economic losses due to bacterial pathogens in the aquaculture industry. Adapted from Maldonado-Miranda et al, (2022).

Host species	Bacterium	Estimated loss (in million USD)	References
<i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i> , <i>Hypophthalmichthys nobilis</i> and <i>Carassius carassius</i>	<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> , <i>Yersinia ruckeri</i> , and <i>Vibrio fluvialis</i>	120	Wei (2002)
<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	<i>Vibrio anguillarum</i>	0.5	Thi-Van et al. (2002)
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	<i>Aeromonas</i> spp., <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> , <i>Flavobacterium columnare</i> , and <i>Streptococcus</i> sp.	4	Kubitza et al. (2013)
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	<i>Aeromonas caviae</i>	0.013	Martins et al. (2008)
Hybrid surubim	<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	0.16	Silva et al. (2012)
<i>Pseudoplatystoma reticulatum</i>	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	Not reported	Pádua et al. (2014)
<i>Seriola</i> spp.	<i>V. anguillarum</i>	200	Gracia-Mendoza (2017)
<i>Ictalurus punctatus</i>	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	10	USDA (2018)
<i>I. punctatus</i> , <i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i> , sport fish, bait fish, and ornamental fish	<i>Flavobacterium columnare</i>	40–50	USDA (2018)
Catfish <i>I. punctatus</i> and Hybrid catfish	<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> virulentas, <i>Edwardsiella ictaluri</i> , and <i>F. columnare</i>	16.9	Peterman (2019)
<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i> , <i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i> , and <i>Salmo salar</i>	<i>Piscirickettsia salmonis</i>	700	Flores-Kossack et al. (2020)
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	<i>Streptococcus agalactinae</i> and <i>Franciella noatunesis</i> sub. <i>Orientalis</i>	0.219	Junior et al. (2020)

1.3.1 *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* in aquaculture

Yersinia ruckeri is mainly known for causing enteric redmouth disease (ERM) in salmonids, and it has a devastating impact on fish populations. This pathogen is characterized by its ability to cause hemorrhaging in the mouth, fins, and internal organs of infected fish, leading to rapid spread and high mortality rates if not managed effectively (Tobback *et al.*, 2007). This happens especially in young fish, disrupting production cycles and affecting economic viability (Barnes *et al.*, 2011). *Yersinia* has also been identified as a causative agent of disease in a variety of fish species, including salmonids and freshwater fish, causing continuous infections that compromise growth and survival.

The transmission of *Yersinia* in aquaculture systems is multifaceted, involving both direct (e.g., contaminated water, infected stock) and indirect (e.g., fomites, vectors) systems. Environmental

stressors, such as poor water quality or overcrowding, increases susceptibility to *Yersinia* infections among cultured organisms, emphasizing the importance of pathogen ecology and aquaculture management practices (Austin *et al.*, 2016).

Aeromonas salmonicida, on the other hand, is known for causing furunculosis, a highly contagious disease affecting salmonids such as salmon and trout. This disease manifests as ulcerative lesions, hemorrhaging, and systemic infections, leading to significant mortality rates in affected populations (Cipriano *et al.*, 2001). Similarly, *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Aeromonas veronii* are associated with diseases in warm-water species, causing symptoms ranging from skin lesions and fin rot to septicemia, depending on the host species and environmental conditions (Austin *et al.*, 2007).

The transmission of *Aeromonas* in aquaculture is influenced by various factors, including water quality, stocking density, and stressors that compromise fish immunity. *Aeromonas* species can persist in aquatic environments, colonizing fish mucosal surfaces or existing as free-living organisms in water and sediment. Transmission can occur through direct contact between infected and susceptible individuals, as well as through waterborne routes, highlighting the complexity of disease management in aquaculture operations (Austin & Austin, 2012).

1.3.2 Detection methods for *Y.ruc* and *A.sal* in aquaculture

Traditional microbiological methods, such as culture-based techniques, remain essential in identifying *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* species from environmental and clinical samples. Selective agar media, supplemented with antibiotics to inhibit competing microflora, facilitate the isolation and listing of *Y.ruc* and *A.sal* colonies based on characteristic growth patterns and biochemical reactions (OIE (World Organization for Animal Health), 2016).

Furthermore, the advancements in molecular biology have revolutionized the detection and characterization of *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* species in aquaculture. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based assays, targeting conserved genetic markers (for example, 16S rRNA, virulence genes), offer rapid and specific identification of *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* pathogens directly from complex matrices, including water, sediment, and fish tissues. Real-time PCR platforms enable quantitative analysis of pathogen load, facilitating epidemiological investigations and risk assessment in aquaculture environments (OIE (World Organisation for Animal Health), 2016).

Furthermore, next-generation sequencing (NGS) technologies provide comprehensive insights into *Y.ruc* and *A.sal* diversity and profiles within aquaculture systems. Metagenomic methods use advanced sequencing techniques to find small amounts of *Y.ruc* and *A.sal* populations and monitor microbial community dynamics associated with disease outbreaks. Bioinformatic tools help compare the genes of *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas*, improving our understanding of how these bacteria cause disease and adapt in water environments (Le Roux *et al.*, 2015).

1.3.3 Importance of detecting *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* in aquaculture

The quick detection of these pathogens in aquaculture is essential for ensuring both animal health and public health. Early identification of infected fish populations enables quick and efficient implementation of disease management strategies, including quarantine measures, treatment interventions, and biosecurity procedures, to limit pathogen spread and minimize economic losses within aquaculture facilities (Austin *et al.*, 2016).

From a public health perspective, the presence of *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* species in aquaculture environments raises concerns regarding food safety and the risks of diseases spreading from animals to humans. *Yersinia*, in particular, has been implicated in foodborne outbreaks associated with contaminated seafood products, emphasizing the importance of monitoring and control measures throughout the aquaculture production chain (Pridgeon *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, due to the presence of these pathogens, there is the excessive and prophylactic use of antibiotics, increasing the chance of antibiotic resistance in humans, which might later result in immunity problems. Surveillance and detection programs targeting *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* pathogens contribute to regulatory compliance and consumer confidence in seafood products, ensuring compliance with food safety standards and mitigating potential health risks posed by these pathogens (Majeed *et al.*, 2023).

1.4 Why are *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* adequate for the experiment?

Selecting *Yersinia ruckeri* and *Aeromonas salmonicida* as the target pathogens for this study is justified by firstly the fact that they belong to the safety risk group 1 and can therefore be reared in TunaTech laboratories and clean cultures can be purchased via DSMZ. Their affordability and easy availability also act in their favor.

Moreover, their significant impact on salmon health and the aquaculture industry is undeniable. These pathogens represent a substantial challenge for fish farmers due to the reasons mentioned

above. But, on the positive side, their presence in diverse aquatic environments, including both freshwater and marine systems and their ability to easily grow in the laboratory makes them ideal candidates for studying the effectiveness of eDNA as a monitoring tool (Gold *et al.*, 2021).

The focus on these pathogens also aligns with the need to develop strong and reliable eDNA detection methods that can be applied across different environmental conditions. Understanding how various storage conditions affect the recovery rates of eDNA from these pathogens will provide valuable insights into optimizing sampling protocols and efficient techniques for broader application in aquaculture and environmental monitoring (Sun *et al.*, 2022).

1.5 Basics of environmental DNA (eDNA) in aquatic environments

eDNA comes from cellular material that organisms shed through processes like excretion, secretion, and natural decay. In water, eDNA can last for different amounts of time depending on factors like water temperature, pH, microbial activity, and UV radiation. These factors affect the physical, enzymatic and chemical reaction of DNA and cause it to break down and spread, influencing how detectable it is in environmental samples (Van der Heyde *et al.*, 2023).

Many studies have shown that eDNA is effective for finding aquatic pathogens. But these studies also point out challenges like eDNA degrading over time, environmental factors affecting its persistence, the risk of contamination during sampling and analysis and the fact that free living bacteria is also filtered during filtration, thus affecting the qPCR values obtained (Ficetola *et al.*, 2008).

Therefore, knowing how to optimize DNA stability and creating methods to keep eDNA intact from collection to analysis is important for reliable pathogen detection (William *et al.*, 2017).

1.6 Experimental design

1.6.1 Experiment background

This research and experiment is performed in affiliation with the PHOTO-SENS project undertaken by TunaTech. This is a multinational innovation project funded under the Horizon 2020 Framework Program of the European Union (Community Research and Development

Information Service (CORDIS), 2020) and under the grant agreement ID: 965643. Along with 4 other companies, TunaTech works to achieve the goal of this project which is the development of a photonic biosensing chip and readout device for the detection of salmon pathogen biomarkers (Surfix BV, 2020). With the chip, the fast and inexpensive detection of DNA-selected disease-causing bacteria, viruses from water-based aquaculture samples shall be implemented (Surfix BV, 2020).

TunaTech has the role of selecting and testing biomarkers for a number of pathogens, including *Yersinia*. For this research, a short, single-stranded DNA sequence is being designed that is specific to its respective target pathogen. This DNA sequence, called probe, is complementary to the DNA of the pathogen. It is used as surface coating on a biosensor chip. When the pathogenic DNA binds to the probe on the chip surface, a short double stranded section is formed. This double stranded section results in a wavelength shift of laser light that is directed at the biosensor. Thus, a change in the wavelength detected by the biosensor indicates the presence of a specific pathogen.

Thus, optimizing the recovery rate of eDNA is of great importance in this research because eDNA will be the material used to analyze the efficiency of the PHOTO-SENS. And TunaTech acts as a testing hub for sent filter papers from aquaculture facilities with the PHOTO-SENS device.

1.6.1 Experiment protocol

The experimental design involves growing and culturing *Yersinia ruckeri* and *Aeromonas salmonicida* in their respective media in the laboratory. After growth, to compare and confirm the presence of Y.ruc and A.sal, a PCR is performed, followed by gel electrophoresis and then the PCR samples are sent for sequencing for final confirmation. After the sequencing results and based on the number of colonies obtained after growth, calculations were made to obtain the required concentration of Y.ruc and A.sal required for filtration. These samples will then undergo filtration to capture the eDNA on filter papers. The filter papers containing the eDNA will then be subjected to various storage conditions, including:

1. **Temperature:** Samples will be stored at room temperature (20°C) and -20°C to evaluate the effect of temperature on eDNA stability.
2. **Preservation Solution:** Some samples will be preserved with 80% ethanol to assess its effectiveness in maintaining eDNA integrity.

3. **Time Intervals:** Samples will be analyzed at different time intervals (1 day, 3 days, 7 days, 10 days and 14 days).

After the respective time interval, these filter papers will then undergo extraction and the last step consists of the sample undergoing a qPCR to quantify and analyze the amount of eDNA recovered.

1.7 Research Objectives

Existing research indicates that storage conditions greatly affect the integrity and recoverability of eDNA. Temperature is a critical factor, with lower temperatures generally preserving DNA integrity better than higher temperatures. Freezing samples at -20°C or lower has been shown to slow down enzymatic degradation and preserve DNA for extended periods. Additionally, the use of preservation solutions such as ethanol can inhibit microbial activity and protect DNA from degradation during storage (Yamanaka *et al.*, 2016).

This study builds on these findings and aims to:

1. Assess the impact of storage temperatures (20°C, -20°C) on eDNA stability and recovery rates.
2. Evaluate the effectiveness of ethanol as a preservation solution for maintaining eDNA integrity.
3. Determine the influence of time intervals (1 day, 3 days, 7 days, 10 days and 14 days) between sample filtration and eDNA extraction on the recovery rates of eDNA.

The results will provide practical guidelines for optimizing eDNA sampling protocols, ensuring that samples remain viable and representative of the target pathogens from the point of collection to analysis.

2. Materials and Methods

(Before and after any experiment, the materials to be used or that were used, were autoclaved).

2.1 Cultivation of bacteria

2.1.1 Preparation of media and plates

For the proper cultivation of the two pathogens, they needed to be inoculated and grown on specific media containing all the necessary nutrients, minerals and conditions for their optimum growth. The media and plates were prepared as recommended in the BacDive Bacterial Diversity Metadatabase by the Leibniz-Institut German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH.

- *Aeromonas* was inoculated and plated on a medium called the M1 media and had the following composition:

-

Table 2: M1 media and M1 plates composition.

M1 Media	M1 Plates
2.5 g Peptone	2.5 g Peptone
1.5 g Meat extract	1.5 g Meat extract
500 ml Water	500 ml Water
no agar added	7.5 g Agar

- *Yersinia* was inoculated and plated on a media called the M535 media and had the following composition:

Table 3: M535 media and M535 plates composition.

M535 Media	M535 Plates
15g Tryptic Soy Broth	15g Tryptic Soy Broth
500 ml water	500 ml water
no agar added	7.5 g Agar

2.1.2 Inoculation of bacteria

Inoculation for the two bacteria was performed in the same way. 50 ml of the bacterium's media was poured into an Erlenmeyer flask and either 500 ml of a previous media containing the bacteria was added to the flask or a pick from an uncontaminated plate containing colonies of the bacteria was taken. For more accuracy and to reduce contamination, the media was poured near the burning flame of a bunsen burner. Or the 50 ml of media needed was prepared directly into a flask and autoclaved. After autoclaving, inoculation could be performed using the steps mentioned above. Then the inoculated flask was closed and put in an inoculator for around 18 to 24 hours, on the shaker, set at 28°C and set at 90 rotations per minute (rpm).

2.1.3 Plating of the bacteria

The plating of both bacteria was done in the same way. After inoculation, if there was apparent growth, then the flasks were removed from the shaker and a dilution series was created. The cultures were usually diluted using their respective media to concentrations of 1:1000000, 1:5000000 and 1:10000000 dilutions. To create the dilution series, the following formula was used,

$$C_1V_1 = C_2V_2,$$

where C₁ is the concentration of the original solution and V₁ is the volume of the original solution, C₂ is the final concentration needed and V₂ is the final volume required.

After the diluted solution was prepared, using a pipette, 50 µl was pipetted into a plate and evenly spread using a flame-sterilized spreader, treated with 70% ethanol before application. Rigorous measures were taken to ensure sterile conditions during plating, for example, it was conducted under a sterile fume hood. Plating was performed in triplicates for all three dilutions. Following plating, the agar plates were carefully sealed with parafilm and labeled with the corresponding concentration and date. They were then incubated at 28°C, for about 48 hours. After plating the

bacterial cultures, aliquots of 50 ml from each corresponding flask were extracted into small Eppendorf tubes for use in the next experimental steps which includes filtration, qPCR or inoculation of a new flask.

2.2 DNA Extraction

Same as for inoculation, DNA extraction can be done using either 500 µl of media containing growth or by using a pick from a plate containing grown colonies.

2.2.1 DNA extraction using chelex solution

A 10% Chelex solution was prepared using 5 g of Chelex and 50 ml of water.

(i) When using directly grown media, first, 500 µl from the media was pipetted into a 1 ml Safe-lock tube. Safe-Lock tubes are used to minimize the risk of opening of the lid and sample evaporation due to heat and pressure build up and centrifuged for 5 mins at 13000 rpm to obtain a pellet and the supernatant. Then using a pipette, the supernatant was removed, and the pellet was used as explained in the steps below.

(ii) When using a pick from a plate containing colonies, then the steps below were performed directly.

Before pipetting the Chelex solution, it was vortexed to ensure that the resin beads are well distributed. Then to the pellet/ pick, 98 µl of Chelex was added and vortexed again to allow the pick/pellet to dissolve into the solution. 2 µl of Proteinase K was then added. Proteinase K was added after vortexing because due to the harsh shaking, the proteinase K could be damaged and become inactive. The samples were then placed onto a thermomixer where the extraction took place in three steps. The first two steps included shaking at 13,000 rpm at 56°C for 20 minutes with a short vortexing between each step. The final step occurred at 99°C and was shaken at the same speed for 20 minutes. Chelex protocols make use of high temperatures to denature cells and release their DNA into the solution (Simon *et al.*, 2020).

During this step at 99°C, the Chelex resins formed bonds with the positively charged ions to maximize enzymatic digestion of cell components while preventing DNA degradation. After the three heating steps, the samples were centrifuged again for 5 minutes at 15,000 rpm in order to precipitate the cell debris. 50 µl of the supernatant, now containing the extracted DNA, was then collected into new tubes, labeled and stored at -20°C until further use. The rest was discarded.

2.2.2 DNA extraction using extraction kits

Extraction kits were sometimes used to check accuracy and compare the bands of normal DNA extraction and those extraction using DNA kits, seen after gel electrophoresis. One common extraction kit used was the Monarch Plasmid mini-Prep kit (New England Biolabs). It could be used for both the situation of grown media or a direct pick. The steps for each extraction kit are unique to the brand and can be found on the manual of the corresponding kit.

2.3 PCR (polymerase chain reaction)

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) is a widely used molecular biology technique that allows for the amplification of specific DNA sequences. It was developed by Kary Mullis in 1983. PCR works through a series of temperature cycles that facilitate the replication of a target DNA sequence. The process begins with denaturation, where the double-stranded DNA is heated to around 94-98°C to separate it into two single strands. This is followed by annealing, where the temperature is lowered to 50-65°C to allow short DNA primers to bind to their complementary sequences on the single-stranded DNA templates. The final step is extension, where the temperature is raised to around 72°C, the optimal temperature for Taq polymerase, an enzyme that synthesizes new DNA strands by adding nucleotides to the primers. These steps are repeated typically 25-35 times, doubling the amount of target DNA with each cycle and resulting in exponential amplification of the specific DNA sequence of interest. The figure below provides a demonstration of the process (Canene-Adams et al., 2013).

Figure 1: Polymerase chain reaction schematic. 1) Denaturation of DNA double-strand into single-stranded DNA. 2) Primer annealing at single strands. 3) Elongation of double-stranded sequence by complementary addition of nucleotides. DNA is amplified through multiple repetitions of these steps, with the amount of DNA doubling in each cycle (Source: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/9/96/Polymerase_chain_reaction.svg).

For the PCR, a non-species-specific 16S rRNA primer set with the 16S gene, the *Yersinia*-specific PCR primer with the *glnA* gene and *Aeromonas*-specific PCR primer with the *vapA* gene, were set up and based on the PCR required, the respective primer set was used. The primers, consisting of the primer probe for quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) were specifically devised for both bacterial strains by Dr. Florian Borutta and provided by IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies Inc).

Table 4: Sequences of *Y.ruc* PCR primers, 16S primers and *A.sal* primers.

Primer set		Sequence (5' → 3'), coding strand	Length
Y.ruc	PCR Forward primer	ATGGCTCCTCGATTGGTG	18 bp
	PCR Reverse primer	CCATCGTCCCGCAGTAAA	18 bp
A.sal	PCR Forward primer	TTTCTGGCGTAGGCCGTTTA	20 bp
	PCR Reverse primer	GGTGAAGTTAATGACGTTTCGGAAG	24 bp

16S	PCR Forward primer	CCTACGGG <u>N</u> GGC <u>W</u> GCAG (whereas N stands for any base and W is either A or T.)	17 bp
	PCR Reverse primer	GACTACH <u>V</u> GGGTATCTAATC C (whereas H stands for A or C or T and V for A or C or G)	21 bp

The first step, before the PCR execution, was the preparation of a master mix, consisting of specific components obtained from the Biosell company and the exact amount added to the mastermix for one sample is noted in Table 3. For the different PCRs, only the forward and reverse primers differ as they are specific to the program being used. Apart from the primers, for all three PCRs, the other components remained the same.

Table 5: Composition of PCR master mix for 1 sample.

Component	Amount in μ l
Buffer	1.25
dNTPs	0.25
Forward Primer	0.25
Reverse Primer	0.25
Magnesium Chloride	1
Taq Polymerase	0.1
Solution S(to increase efficiency)	1.25
Water	7,15

Each sample was composed of 11.5 μ l of the MasterMix, and then 1 μ l of the DNA extracted was added to it. Usually, the mastermix was prepared for two additional samples to compensate for potential pipetting errors. PCR was then performed in a SensoQuest Labcycler Gradient (Thermoblock 96 wells). The PCR programs were adapted from a 16S rDNA program by Klindworth et al (2012) up to 30 cycles and an annealing temperature of 55°C was chosen. The program used included the following steps:

1. Initial denaturation (this step ensures the complete denaturation of the DNA template) at 95°C for 5 minutes; 30 cycles of denaturation (each cycle begins with denaturation to separate the DNA strands) at 95°C for 40 seconds.
2. Primer annealing (the annealing temperature varies based on the melting temperature (T_m) of the primers) used for each gene. Typically, it is set about 3-5°C below the T_m of the primers) at 55°C for 2 minutes.
3. Extension (the extension time should be adjusted based on the length of the target amplicon, generally 1 minute per kilobase (kb) of the target DNA) at 72°C for 1 minute.
4. Final extension step (the final extension step ensures that any remaining single-stranded DNA is fully extended) at 72°C for 7 minutes.

The *glnA* and *vapA* PCR programs were also established the same way and following Table 16 (in the Annex). The PCR cycler then kept the samples at 8°C until they were removed. Subsequently, the DNA extracted from each bacterial strain underwent PCR procedures tailored to their respective programs.

PCR works together with gel electrophoresis to furnish rapid and efficient confirmation of the presence of the targeted bacteria.

2.4 Gel Electrophoresis

After the completion of the PCR, a gel electrophoresis was performed. First a 1% agarose gel was prepared. The preparation consisted of firstly measuring 0.6 g agarose and adding it to 60 ml of TAE buffer. Then the mixture was heated in a microwave for about 75 seconds. After heating, 5 microlitres of Roti Gel Stain was added. The last step consisted of casting the gel, by pouring the mixture into a 60 ml setting tray to solidify. After 10 mins, the gel was ready, and was introduced into the electrophoretic chamber filled with a TAE buffer. A DNA ladder, comprising DNA fragments ranging from 100 to 1000 base pairs, was pipetted into the wells next to the 5 μ l of each PCR product, which were mixed with 1.2 μ l of loading dye. The gel underwent electrophoresis at 100 V for 30 minutes, resulting in distinct bands of varying lengths. Lastly, for

analysis, the gel was placed under UV light, and the bands could be observed while taking the necessary protective measure of wearing a protective face shield.

2.5 Sequencing

Sequencing is a process performed to obtain and confirm the identity of the bacteria being experimented on. It is also a very useful tool to detect contaminants in samples. After undergoing PCR, the samples were prepared according to the table below. The DNA template used was the PCR product obtained. And the forward and reverse primers were added separately to two different tubes.

Table 6: Sequencing mix composition for 1 sample.

Components	Amount in μ l
H2O	6.5
forward/reverse primer	2.5
DNA template	1

When the tubes were ready, they were then sent to the company, Macrogen Europe for sequencing. The sequencing results were then identified and compared using the BLASTN tool from NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information).

2.6 qPCRs (Quantitative Polymerase Chain reaction)

2.6.1 Introduction of qPCR

Quantitative PCR (qPCR) stands as an essential molecular biology method extensively applied for the accurate quantification of DNA. At its core, qPCR is responsible for the real-time surveillance of DNA amplification in each reaction cycle. For the qPCR procedure, Dr. Florian Borutta designed specific primers and SYBR probes were used. Although fluorescently labeled probes are usually responsible for targeted genes, in this research, SYBR probes were the better option. SYBR Green binds nonspecifically to double-stranded DNA (dsDNA), emitting fluorescence upon binding, which makes the assay design easier by eliminating the need for

pathogen-specific probes (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2015). This universal binding mechanism reduces the initial setup cost and time, making it particularly useful for studies involving multiple pathogens like *Y.ruc* and *A.sal*. Additionally, the broad applicability of SYBR Green allows for more straightforward optimization of reaction conditions and easier detection of non-specific amplifications, which can be crucial for accurately assessing eDNA degradation under different storage conditions (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2015).

These molecular tools are essential in the amplification and quantification of the nucleic acid of interest. As DNA amplifies, the fluorescence signal increases proportionately, and the cycle at which the signal surpasses a predefined threshold is recorded. This recorded threshold cycle, quantification cycle in which a fluorescence signal exceeds a baseline threshold value in qPCR, (Cq) value serves as crucial information about the initial quantity of the target DNA present in the sample (Taylor *et al.*, 2018).

2.6.2 Creation of a Standard Dilution Series from *Y.ruc* PCR product

For the creation of a standard dilution series, a PCR of extracted DNA from *Yersinia ruckeri* was performed with the *glnA* primer set. The PCR products were used for gel electrophoresis on the 1 % agarose gel. After gel electrophoresis, two DNA bands, with positive results confirming the presence of *Y.ruc* were cut out from the agarose gel, measured and transferred to 2 ml Safe-Lock tubes. The DNA was then extracted from the gel slices with the QIAEX® II Gel Extraction Kit, following the manufacturer's quick-start protocol. The gel extracted DNA was then measured on a NanoDrop™ One from Thermo Scientific™. Each sample was measured three times. The extract, giving the most accurate result, was chosen for the creation of a standard series, that is the extract with the highest DNA concentration and the highest A260/280 purity ratio. The following formula was applied to calculate the copies/μl in the DNA extracts:

$$\frac{\bar{c}_{NanoDrop}(\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}) \times 10^{-9} \text{g}/\text{ng} \times N_A(\text{copies}/\text{mol})}{MW(\text{mol}/\mu\text{L})} = c_{\text{calculated}}(\text{copies}/\mu\text{L})$$

- $\bar{c}_{NanoDrop}$: mean of three DNA concentration measurements performed with NanoDrop™ One
- N_A : Avogadro's constant (6.022×10^{23} molecules/mol);
1 molecule $\cong$ 1 DNA copy
- MW : molecular weight of the PCR amplicon

The molecular weight of the PCR amplicon was obtained by entering the sequence of the PCR product into an online calculator for the molecular weight of DNA and choosing dsDNA as output (https://www.bioinformatics.org/sms2/dna_mw.html).

Based on the calculated copies/ μ l in the measured extracts, dilutions were performed to reach a concentration of 100 million copies/ μ l. From this starting concentration, a dilution series was prepared in steps of 10, down to 10 copies/ μ l. These samples with known concentrations were then used as standard series for quantification of unknown samples.

2.6.3 Creation of a Standard Dilution Series from gBlocks Gene Fragment

For *Aeromonas*, due to some contamination problems, explained further in the results and discussion part, it was more accurate to create a standard dilution series from a gBlocks Gene Fragment that was ordered from IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies Inc). These series consist of artificial DNA sequences with known concentrations, designed to resemble the target gene. The *A.sal* 5'-3' gBlocks sequence was the following:

```
TGCCACCGGCAGTGCCATCCGGTCACATGACTACACCACGTTAATAGCGATCTGGCTTTTT  
TGGCGTAGGCCGTTTACCGGTCTGCTGGTTAACCCGAATGATCATGGTAATTTTGCCAATA  
GCGGTGAAGTTAATGACGTTCCGGAAGCTGGTCGTGGTGAAGCTAAGCGCAAGGCAAATGCA  
TTTAGCCAAATTTATGCGTGCTTTG
```

They are high-fidelity double-stranded DNA fragments that undergo a post-synthesis quality control including size verification by capillary electrophoresis and sequence identification by mass spectrometry (Balážová *et al.*, 2020). The freeze-dried gBlocks Gene Fragments were resuspended following the manufacturer's instructions.

Since the concentration of *A.sal* in the tube was 7.79 fmol/ng, the formula used was the following:

$$77.9 \frac{\text{fmol}}{\mu\text{L}} * 10^{-15} * 6.022 * 10^{23} = 4.69 * 10^{10} = 4\,690\,000\,000\,000 \text{ copies per } 1 \mu\text{L},$$

Thus, to set up the dilution series for *A.sal*, 1 μ l of the gBlocks solution was added to a tube with 429 μ l of molecular grade water. A normal dilution series was carried out from this tube in intervals of 10, ranging from 100 million copies down to 10 copies/ μ l.

2.6.4 Quantification of bacterial load

Unknown samples were prepared after the calculation of colony forming units (CFU) obtained from the number of colonies counted on agar plates, plated with a 1:1,000,000, a 1:5,000,000 and a 1:10000000 dilution. CFU counts, adjusted for dilution factors, were averaged, and this value was employed to estimate the original bacterial quantity in around 1 ml of the initial culture. Subsequent dilutions were performed to achieve the needed bacterial cell concentration. The bacterial cell concentration required for *Y.ruc* was 100 million, 10 million and 1 million; while for *A.sal*, it was 1 million and 250K.

2.6.5 Preparation of samples for qPCR

After the setting up of the gBlocks dilution series and the CFU dilution series, a qPCR was performed using the Bio-Rad C1000 Touch Thermal Cycler as well as the CFX Maestro™ software. Same as for the PCR, for the qPCR also, a mastermix was prepared and then 9 µl of the mastermix was added to 1 µl of the component to be tested. The mastermix was prepared following Table 5. The samples were then placed in the Cycler and the qPCR program was started.

Table 7: qPCR Mastermix composition for 1 sample.

Components	Amount / µl
SSOAdvanced Supermix	5
Forward qPCR primer	0.1
Reverse Forward Primer	0.1
Water	3.8

For quantification of bacterial DNA via qPCR, a standard series must be included in the qPCR run next to the samples to be analyzed. By defining the standard series as such in the qPCR software (CFX Maestro™™ Software Version 2.2), a standard curve is created automatically, and the starting concentrations of unknown samples are determined based on their position on the standard curve. This process can also be performed manually by plotting the C_q values of the

standard against the logarithmic starting quantity. Unknown samples (x) can then be quantified based on their Cq value, using the y-intercept and slope of the standard curve:

$$SQ_x = 10^{\left(\frac{Cq_x - (y\text{-intercept})}{\text{slope}}\right)}$$

2.7 Filtration

2.7.1 Filtration procedure

After inoculation and collection of grown media, a filtration experiment was carried out to imitate the extraction and analysis of environmental DNA (eDNA). Since the CFU values of both bacteria were quite big, only a small volume of aliquots was used. Thus, instead of 1 liter of distilled water which is usually used, only 100 ml was spiked with liquid bacterial culture ranging from 1 billion cells down to 1 million for *Yersinia* and from 1 million to 250 K for *Aeromonas*. The filter apparatus was set up as shown in the figure below and the filtration process always started with the lower number of cell copies and ended with the highest number of cell copies.

Figure 2: Filtration setup. Left: Full setup including filter paper. Right top: setup without glass piece. Right bottom: Close-up of rubber seals (D) and metal sieve (G) on filter cone (E). Source: Bachelor thesis: Gesa Birkenbach.

The metal filter sieve is first disinfected using 70% ethanol and subjected to flame sterilization before each filtration process. Glass fiber filters (45 mm pore size), capable of retaining bacterial cells, were positioned atop the filter cone. A vacuum pump was then activated during the filtration process. Based on the calculation, the amount of bacterial culture was pipetted into 100 ml of distilled water and subsequently filtered. The process was repeated for each sample twice with washing of the apparatus after each sample. The filters, collected in Petri dishes, were left at approximately 35°C for approximately 30 minutes to facilitate drying.

2.7.2 Filter papers after drying

After drying, one set of filter papers consisting of each concentration to be analyzed is taken and undergoes extraction and qPCR. This set was considered as the reference and used to determine the recovery rate. The remaining filter papers were then stored under the different storage conditions mentioned below and each condition were subjected to each of the time intervals also mentioned in Table 8

Table 8: The conditions and time interval for the storage of filter papers.

Storage conditions	Dry at room temperature in a closed petri dish	Dry at -20°C in a closed petri dish	Stored in 80% Ethanol at room temperature	Stored in 80% Ethanol at -20°C	-
Time intervals	1 day	3 days	7 days	10 days	14 days

2.7.3 DNA extraction from filter papers

The filter papers were then cut into small fragments using two tweezers to avoid contamination and added to a 2 ml Safe-lock tube containing 990 µl of the 10% chelex solution and 10 µl of Proteinase K. Then a standard DNA extraction protocol was carried out.

2.7.4 qPCR of filtered paper after DNA extraction

These samples, alongside their respective gBlocks standard series, underwent a subsequent qPCR analysis. The quantification results obtained were then utilized to calculate the recovery rate for the bacteria using the following formula:

$$\text{Recovery rate} = [\text{cq value after storage} / \text{cq value on reference day}] \text{ multiplied by } 100.$$

After calculating the recovery rate, the efficiency of the techniques to test the effect of storage conditions on the eDNA recovery rate of salmon pathogens can be analyzed.

3. Results

In this research, two different pathogens with their own structure have been used. Hence the results obtained for each bacteria will be different depending on their physical and chemical properties. Thus, the results part will be separated into two parts: the results obtained from *Yersinia* and the second part will be from the experiments with *Aeromonas*.

3.1 Yersinia Results

3.1.1 Bacterial growth

For this experiment, a fresh batch of *Yersinia* was grown under normal laboratory conditions and although sterile precautions were taken, at first, some contaminations did occur during the bacterial growth. A clean grown media containing *Yersinia* has a yellowish-orange appearance and the clean colonies formed on the plates have a yellowish and bull eye- like appearance. As seen in figure 3, contamination appears in the form of overgrown colonies, clusters, white or dark yellowish spots.

Figure 3: Contaminated *Yersinia* plates - with overgrown colonies, white spot like colonies and clusters of grown *Yersinia*.

Thus, to remediate this problem, sterile precautions were enhanced, and before inoculation, the amount of media to be inoculated were first autoclaved and then used for inoculation. And concerning the plating, it was then done under fume hoods and in a second lab which is usually not used for the cultivation of other bacteria. After undertaking these measures, clean and uniform growth could be seen. Figure 4 shows the uniform growth of *Yersinia* in a flask while figure 5 shows the uniform appearance of *Yersinia* colonies.

Figure 4: The uniform growth of *Yersinia* in M535 media.

Figure 5: Clean M535 plates containing the uniform growth of *Yersinia* with the yellowish bull-like appearance.

To assess the growth of *Yersinia*, two methods could be used: either measure the optical density (OD) of the culture samples or count the colony forming units (CFU) obtained from the plates. And in this experiment, the second option was chosen. After around 48 hours, the number of colonies were ready to be counted and analyzed. The average cell number per μl of original culture was calculated for each plate and the average was noted for further calculations. An overview can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9: CFU counts of plating experiments, including calculated average cell number/μl.

Dilution	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Average cells/μl
1: 1 000000	Too many to count	Too many to count	Too many to count	-
1: 5 000 000	208	191	158	1856666.667
1: 10 000 000	100	96	92	960 000

After obtaining the average cells/μl, further calculations were carried out to estimate the amount of μl needed to obtain the concentration of cells for filtration. The following formula was used:

$$\text{Volume of culture sample needed per } \mu\text{l} = \text{number of cells required} / \text{average cell copies per } \mu\text{l}$$

For *Yersinia*, 100 million, 10 million and 1 million cell copies were required. Thus, the formula was used, and the following results were obtained:

Table 10: Volume of culture sample required to achieve the number of cell copies required.

Cell copies needed	Volume of culture samples required/μl
1 million	130
10 million	13
100 million	1.3

3.1.2 Gel Electrophoresis

After the CFU count, a PCR was performed to firstly confirm the presence and purity of the *Yersinia* colonies and culture sample. And secondly, it was performed to obtain the PCR product needed to create the standard series for qPCR quantification. Figure 6 shows the agarose gel

that was used to check for successful PCR amplification and the 100 bp to 1000 bp ladder that was used to compare the results. The figure is displayed in black and white to make the bands more visible and distinguishable.

Figure 6: Agarose gel of PCR products with *Yersinia ruckeri*- specific PCR primers (369 base pairs) and their 100 to 1000 bp DNA ladder (369 base pairs)- On the left is the DNA ladder, then the first four samples are 4 picks from M535 plates, shown in figure 5. Samples 5, 6 and 7 are samples taken from the inoculated flask containing growth as shown in figure 4. The 8th sample is a positive control and the last sample is a NTC control.

3.1.3 Sequencing

Before the creation of the standard series, the Y1 and Y2 PCR product was sent for sequencing to MacroGen Europe, and the purity and presence of *Yersinia* was confirmed by MacroGen Europe. The following sequence was obtained:

Figure 7: Sequence result provided by Macrogen Europe.

The figure shows a four-color chromatogram generated by an automated sequencing machine for the glnA PCR product. Each of the nitrogenous bases is indicated by a specific color: adenine (green), cytosine (blue), guanine (black), and thymine (red). The sequence was analyzed in BLAST (nucleotide blast-blastn) and compared with the NCBI database and the presence of *Yersinia* and similarity with *Yersinia Ruckeri* was confirmed to be around 99.13%.

Sequences producing significant alignments		Download	Select columns	Show				
Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain SC09 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3799871	CP025800
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NHV_3758 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3766700	CP023184
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain Barren Creek chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3791418	CP133440
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-492 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3654750	CP099813
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-9681 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3765355	CP099811
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-10567 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3700651	CP099809
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-11076 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3763098	CP099808
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-10705 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3818566	CP099805
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-10571 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3782452	CP098724
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-11267 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3818184	CP098719
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-11294 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3818138	CP098716
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-1176 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3829172	CP098714
☒ Yersinia ruckeri strain NVI-1292 chromosome, complete genome	Yersinia ruckeri	619	1139	95%	3e-172	99.13%	3765691	CP098711

Figure 8: Comparison of sequencing results with NCBI database.

3.1.4 Creation of a Quantification Standard

After obtaining the sequencing result, the standard series for the Y.ruc quantification was created using the Y1 and Y2 PCR product, from the gel electrophoresis shown in figure 6 and spanning the qPCR primer region. The PCR products were extracted from the agarose gel as described in the materials and methods section. The DNA extracts were then measured three times on the NanoDrop™, to assess the DNA concentration and purity. The A260/280 ratio is used to assess protein impurity samples. A value between the range of 1.8 to 2.0 is the reference value for pure DNA (Chen *et al.*, 2011). The resulting average values, standard deviation (std) and purity are displayed in Table 11.

Table 11: Concentration and purity measurements of Y1 and Y2 PCR products extracted from an agarose gel.

	Nucleic acid (ng/μl)		A260/280 purity	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std
Y1	21	1.539	1.698	0.031
Y2	15.7	1.257	1.451	0.062

Since Y1 had the higher concentration and the higher value regarding pure DNA, it was the product selected for the standard series. The number of copies per μl were calculated using the equation provided in the materials and methods part, with the molecular weight of 44 525.76 Da and the information provided in Table 11. However, since the value obtained was too big and would not be reliable for the experiment, the extract was diluted, using a 1:10 dilution and the new number of copies per μl was estimated to be 1.85×10^9 . Then to obtain the standard series ranging from 100 million copies to 10 copies, first 54 μl of water was added to 3 μl of the extract to obtain the starting 100 million copies. And from the 100 million copies, a 1: 10 dilution was performed to obtain the other series until the 10 copies.

A positive control was also added to check if the qPCR works properly, while a negative and NTC was added to check for any contamination in the mastermix used and to check that the qPCR program is working properly and is not also detecting unwanted products.

Starting Quantity	Cq values			Log (SQ)	Mean
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3		
100000000	13.37	14	14.65	8	14.01
10000000	17.27	17.46	18.82	7	17.85
1000000	20.66	20.5	21.89	6	21.02
100000	26.06	24.48	26.79	5	25.78
10000	25.03	27.03	29.03	4	27.03
1000	28.45	28.22	30.86	3	29.18
100	30.94	30.73	32.06	2	31.24
Positive Control	16.04	16.97	16.96		
Negative Control	N/A	N/A	39.89		
NTC	N/A	38.87	39.06		
Efficiency/%	125.2	128	116.5		
R^2	0.98	0.95	0.96		
Slope	2.84	2.79	2.98		

Figure 9: Overview of the prepared standard series performance. Several trials were performed and to obtain the most accurate value, the mean was calculated and these mean values were taken later when comparing the Cq values obtained from the filter papers after storage.

Standard Series curve

Figure 10: qPCR CFU standard curve. Plotted from average values of several qPCR runs. The line equation obtained, $Y = -2.87X + 38.1$, with the efficiency of 120 % obtained, can be used for quantification of samples with unknown sample quantities.

From Figure 9 and Figure 10, it can be seen that the standard series from 100 million copies to 100 copies was successfully achieved. Also the R² values are on average 0.95, which is in the

correct range of 0.90 to 1.00 for reliable results. The efficiency shows that the experiment was performed correctly, but there were some anomalies. This is noted because normally, the range for the efficiency is around 90 -100 %, but in this experiment carried out, for *Yersinia*, the efficiency has ranged between 116 % to 128 %. This might be due to some pipetting errors or some small contamination problems, which will be further elaborated in the discussion part. This statement is enhanced due to the slight positive value obtained for the negative control and NTC, which should not have normally been detected by the qPCR. Degradation might also have occurred because the Cq value increases over time, indicating that the concentration of the targeted product is decreasing.

3.1.5 Quantification Experiment

After filtration, 2 sets of three filter papers with 100 million, 10 million and 1 million copies respectively underwent extraction and filtration and were considered as the reference Cq value. These Cq values will then be later used to compare the Cq value of the other filtrates which were stored under the different storage conditions. And the recovery rate would then be calculated from the two values obtained.

Table 12: Yersinia Reference Cq values

Number of cell copies	Average Reference Cq value (the average reference of the 2 sets of filter papers)- Day 0
100 million	23.43
10 million	26.02
1 million	28.05

While the first two sets were taken as reference, the other filter papers were kept under their respective storage conditions and also underwent extraction and qPCR after the different time intervals. The eDNA degradation of the three cell copies number, the comparison between the different storage conditions and their respective recovery rate can be observed below. For each storage condition, there were two filter papers with their respective concentration and the average Cq value was calculated and recorded in the excel below.

100 million		Cq value			
		Dry at r.t.p	Dry at -20 °C	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20°C
	Reference day	23.43	-	-	-
	Day 1	23.96	24.05	24.39	25.31
	Day 3	27.83	23.22	24.48	23.77
	Day 7	29.41	23.93	24.37	23.44
	Day 10	29.55	23.58	27.89	24.65
	Day 14	34.92	24.57	31.39	26.39
%Recovery rate ([cq day (0) / cq day (d)] multiply by 100)					
	Day	Dry at r.t.p	Dry at -20	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20 °C
	1	97.79	97.42	96.06	92.57
	3	84.19	100.9	95.71	98.57
	7	79.66	97.91	96.14	99.96
	10	79.28	99.36	84.01	95.05
	14	67.11	95.36	74.64	88.78

Figure 11: The Cq value of the 100 million cell copies' filtrates after undergoing the different storage conditions and their respective recovery rates.

10 million		Cq value			
		Dry at r.t.p	Dry at -20 °C	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20°C
	Reference day	26.02	-	-	-
	Day 1	27.82	26.53	29.58	27.98
	Day 3	33.57	27.21	30.84	29.4
	Day 7	34.01	28.11	29.98	29.67
	Day 10	34.04	29.77	34.73	29.71
	Day 14	34.58	31.29	34.89	30.58
%Recovery rate ([cq day (0) / cq day (d)] multiply by 100)					
	Day	Dry at r.t.p	Dry at -20	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20 °C
	1	93.53	98.08	87.97	92.99
	3	77.5	95.63	84.37	88.5
	7	76.51	92.56	86.79	87.7
	10	76.44	87.4	74.92	87.58
	14	75.25	83.16	74.57	85.09

Figure 12: The Cq value of the 10 million cell copies' filtrates after undergoing the different storage conditions and their respective recovery rates.

1 million		Cq value			
		Dry at r.t.p	Dry at -20 °C	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20°C
	Reference day	28.05	-	-	-
	Day 1	31.26	27.64	28.2	27.56
	Day 3	33.15	31.35	34.24	30.79
	Day 7	36.02	31.89	35.25	31.92
	Day 10	37.32	32.4	33.46	32.39
	Day 14	34.89	32.86	32.28	33.29
%Recovery rate ([cq day (0) / cq day (d)] multiply by 100)					
	Day	Dry at r.t.p	Dry at -20	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20 °C
	1	89.73	101.5	99.47	101.8
	3	84.62	89.47	81.92	91.1
	7	77.87	87.96	79.57	87.88
	10	75.16	86.57	83.83	86.6
	14	80.4	85.36	86.9	84.26

Figure 13: The Cq value of the 1 million cell copies' filtrates after undergoing the different storage conditions and their respective recovery rates.

Based on the Cq values recorded from the filtration under different conditions, it is clearly observed that lower storage temperatures and the use of ethanol as a preservation solution significantly enhance eDNA stability and recovery rates, irrespective of the cell copies number. Specifically, storage at -20°C consistently yielded higher recovery rates compared to room temperature storage. Although some small anomalies can be seen in the trend, most of the time, the difference in recovery rate when stored under the two conditions ranged from 10% to 20%, in favor of -20°C. Moreover, preservation with ethanol, being the second-best storage condition, gave a high recovery rate ranging from 80% to 99% and was particularly effective in maintaining eDNA integrity at lower temperatures. However, the combination of ethanol and low temperature resulted in a lower percentage of recovery rate over time compared to filter papers only stored at -20°C. Additionally, the timing between sample filtration and processing proved to be essential, with notable eDNA degradation of around 10% to 20% occurring in unpreserved samples left at room temperature for over 24 hours.

Moreover, when quantifying the filtrate DNA and comparing it with the Cq values from the standard series, it can be seen that the values obtained are slightly higher than expected. Due to the extraction and filtration, the Cq values of the filtrated DNA should be equal to the Cq value of one standard series which is 10 times lower than its concentration. For example, the 100 million copies

should be compared to the 10 million standard series value. From figures 9 and 11, it can be seen that the Cq value is around 4.20 higher than expected. This phenomenon in the trend includes, for example, some Cq values recorded on day 7 are lower than that recorded on day 3, and normally it should be the opposite since degradation occurs over time. This anomaly might be due to small errors occurring during filtration, for example, when dealing with a high number of filtrates, the time between filtration and storage might differ for each filtrate, thus exposing them to some contaminants. This aspect will be further elaborated in the discussion part.

Thus, from the results, the most to least efficient storage conditions are: dry at -20°C, preserved in ethanol at -20°C, preserved at room temperature in ethanol, and finally, dry at room temperature. Irrespective of the cell copies number and storage conditions, the timing between sample filtration and processing will always cause degradation of eDNA.

3.2 Aeromonas Results

3.2.1 Bacterial growth

For *Aeromonas*, as compared to *Y.ruc*, it was a bit difficult to grow a fresh culture due to the high contamination rate. Similarly, *Y.ruc*, *A.sal* contamination appears like clusters, dark yellowish colonies as it can be seen in figure 14.

Figure 14: An *A.sal* contaminated plate.

Thus, old plates and an old culture sample stored as aliquots were used for filtration and its corresponding set of 1:1000000 dilution plates were taken for the experiment. Figure 15

demonstrates clean whitish transparent colonies on a plate. These aliquots and colonies were from a batch cultivated around 7 months prior to the experiment.

Figure 15: A M1 plate containing clean whitish-transparent *A.sal* colonies.

To assess the growth of *A.sal*, the colony forming units (CFU) obtained from the plates were counted. Since old plates containing colonies of the culture to be used for filtration were used, there was no need to wait for growth. The number of colonies were counted from 3 of the 1: 1000000 and the average cell number per μl of original culture was calculated for each plate and the average was noted for further calculations. An overview can be seen in Table 13.

Table 13: *A.sal* CFU counts of plating experiments, including calculated average cell number/ μl .

Dilution	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Average cells/ μl
1: 1 000000	50	25	5	256,600

After obtaining the average cells/ μl , further calculations were carried out to estimate the amount of microlitres needed to obtain the concentration of cells for filtration. The following formula was used:

$$\text{Volume of culture sample} \frac{\text{needed}}{\mu\text{l}} = \text{number of cells required} \div \text{average cell} \frac{\text{copies}}{\mu\text{l}}$$

For *A.sal*, because there were not enough culture samples, only 1 million and 250 k cell copies were used. Thus, the formula was used, and the following results were obtained:

Table 14: Volume of culture sample required to achieve the number of cell copies required.

Cell copies needed	Volume of culture samples required/ μ l
250 K	66.98
1 million	267

3.2.2 Gel electrophoresis

Same as for *Y.ruc*, a *vapA* PCR was carried out to confirm the presence of *A.sal* and the following result was obtained.

Figure 16: Gel after electrophoresis with vapA PCR products and passed through UV light. The first four wells contain samples with freshly extracted Aeromonas extract (2 of which were from the aliquots and the other two were DNA extracted from 2 A.sal colonies), 5th one was a positive control (a previous extract which gave a positive result), 6th sample was a negative control (A Yersinia extract) and the last sample was a negative template control (NTC) which is usually just water.

Sometimes, when neither the *Yersinia* nor the *Aeromonas* gel electrophoresis would be reliable or conclusive, then a 16s PCR and gel electrophoresis would be carried out to confirm the presence of any bacteria. The 16s gene is a highly conserved gene in bacteria and has long been used for bacterial identification and is present in both *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas*.

Figure 17: The result of a 16s Bact gel electrophoresis under UV light. The first 6 bands are supposed to be Aeromonas, the 7th one is a Yersinia control and the last one is a NTC control.

As it can be observed, samples 2, 3, 4 and 6 gave a strong bright band while sample 1 and 5 gave a weak band, which might be due to extraction error, pipetting error or low DNA concentration.

3.2.3 Sequencing

Before filtration, the 16s PCR product of 2 bands giving positive A.sal results were sent for sequencing and after two days, it was confirmed that it was A.sal. The sequence was then compared in the NCBI database, confirming the 99.97% similarity with *Aeromonas salmonicida*.

3.2.4 Creation of a gBlocks Standard Series

An overview of several qPCR runs with the gBlocks standard series can be found in figure 18, which also shows the calculated average Cq value for the different starting quantities. Together with the standard series, same as for Y.ruc, a positive, negative and NTC was also added as control and to monitor if the qPCR program is working properly and if there is any sign of contamination in any reagents used for the Mater mix. The lowest starting quantity that was detected in all runs was 10 cells.

gBlock Standard series								
	1st Trial	2nd trial	3rd Trial	4th trial	5th Trial		Log (SQ)	Mean
100 mil	10.54	9.47	15.66	18.42	16.33		8	14.08
10 mil	15.15	14.17	20.4	24.96	21.36		7	19.21
1 mil	19.52	18.16	25.21	29.31	25.41		6	23.55
100k	21.99	22.35	31.31	33.62	29.75		5	27.8
10k	25.75	26.14	35.26	38.7	34.59		4	32.09
1k	29.03	29.64	39.06	-	37.05		3	33.7
100	31.53	32.28	-	-	38.75		2	34.19
10	34.14	35.51	-		39.79		1	36.48

Figure 18: The different qPCR runs of the gBlocks standard series and the average Cq values.

The average Cq values were plotted against the LOG starting quantity in an average standard curve, as shown in figure 19, with an efficiency of 106.5 % and a R² of 0.941.

Figure 19: Average Cq value plotted against the LOG starting quantity with the line equation of $Y = -3.17 X + 41.9$.

From figure 18 and 19, it can be seen that with the A.sal gBlocks, a standard series was successfully achieved. The standard series was considered pretty accurate because after plotting the average cq value v/s the log (SQ), the efficiency obtained was 106.5% and the R² was 0.941. These measurements fit perfectly in the range of values which are considered as accurate when performing qPCR. Moreover, when comparing the standard series, efficiency

and R² value of A.sal and Y.ruc, it can be seen that the gBlocks is a bit more accurate than the self-made Y.ruc standard series. This can be explained by the fact that the gBlocks is already prepared by a manufacturer while for Y.ruc, the standard series was prepared and established from scratch in the lab, where the probability of contamination and errors is higher. And when analyzing the different qPCR runs, some small anomalies can also be observed and this might be due to some pipetting errors, some small contamination problems. due to the constant opening and closing of the master mix and standard series tubes as recorded by Y.ruc also.

3.2.5 Quantification experiment

After filtration, one set of two filter papers with 250,000 and 1 million copies respectively underwent extraction and filtration and was considered as the reference Cq value.

Table 15: Aeromonas Reference Cq values.

Number of cell copies	Reference Cq value - Day 0
250 000	27.18
1 million	23.07

The other filter papers were then stored under their respective storage conditions and the time interval was 7 days, 10 days and 14 days. For A.sal, the 1 day and 3 days experiments were not performed due to the lack of culture sample. This problem was encountered because of the contamination problem mentioned above. The eDNA degradation of the two cell copies number, the comparison between the different storage conditions and their respective recovery rate can be observed below.

250 k	Average Cq value			
	Dry at r. t.p	Dry at -20°C	Ethanol at r. t.p	Ethanol at -20 °C
7 days	37.44	32.4	37.51	34.14
10 days	37.67	32.04	38.97	35.27
14 days	38.97	32.82	37.24	36.03
250 K Recovery rate I%				
	Dry at r. t.p	Dry at -20°C	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20°C
7 days	72.6	83.88	72.46	79.61
10 days	72.15	84.83	69.75	77.06
14 days	69.75	82.82	72.99	75.44

Figure 20: The Cq value of the 250 000 cell copies' filtrates after undergoing the different storage conditions and their respective recovery rates.

1 million	Average Cq value			
	Dry at r. t.p	Dry at -20°C	Ethanol at r. t.p	Ethanol at -20 °C
7 days	32.1	30.8	33.16	31.05
10 days	32.66	30.18	34.98	36.53
14 days	34.67	31.17	38.16	35.29
1 million Recovery rate I%				
	Dry at r. t.p	Dry at -20°C	Ethanol at r.t.p	Ethanol at -20°C
7 days	71.87	74.9	69.57	74.3
10 days	70.64	76.44	65.95	63.15
14 days	66.54	74.01	60.58	65,37

Figure 21: The Cq value of the 1 million cell copies' filtrates after undergoing the different storage conditions and their respective recovery rates.

Based on the Cq values recorded from the A.sal filtration under different conditions, it is clearly observed that similarly to Y.ruc, lower storage temperatures and the use of ethanol as a

preservation solution significantly enhance eDNA stability and recovery rates, irrespective of the cell copies number. The comparison between the different storage conditions and the bacteria involved are quite similar.

However, it can be noted that the percentage recovery rate, irrespective of the storage conditions, is much lower for *A.sal*. The fact that the culture sample was old might have resulted in a higher degradation rate, leading to a lower detection of eDNA. This statement is based on the fact that the average recovery rate for *Y.ruc* was around 88% whereas for *A.sal*, it is much lower and is estimated to be around 72%. Moreover, when quantifying the filtrate DNA and comparing it with the Cq values from the standard series, it can be seen that the values obtained are slightly higher than expected. However, they are more in range and have a smaller difference, of only around 3.0 as compared to *Y.ruc* which had a difference of around 4.20. But the reasons for this phenomenon and the small anomalies observed in the *A.sal* quantification trend might be similar to that of the reason discussed for *Y.ruc*, because the same techniques were applied for both bacteria. And finally, from the *A.sal* experiment has also concluded that the most to least efficient storage conditions are: dry at -20°C, preserved in ethanol at -20°C, preserved at room temperature in ethanol, and finally, dry at room temperature. Irrespective of the cell copies number and storage conditions, the timing between sample filtration and processing will always cause degradation of eDNA.

4. Discussion

4.1 Summary of Key Findings

The goal of this study was to test and investigate the effects of different storage conditions on the eDNA recovery rate of two distinguished salmon pathogens: *Yersinia ruckerei* and *Aeromonas salmonicida*. The results obtained confirmed the starting hypothesis, which stated that lower temperature and 80% ethanol as a preservative solution and when combined with low temperature act in favor of eDNA recovery and stability. Samples stored at -20°C gave a recovery rate of around 10 to 13% more than the other storage conditions. Interestingly, one of the most unexpected results was that dry storage at -20°C gave a higher recovery rate than samples stored in ethanol at -20°C. This contradicts some existing research and assumptions and might be due to some contamination or human error, which will be further discussed below. Thus, the trend observed from best to least efficient storage condition was: stored at -20°C, stored in ethanol at -20°C, stored in ethanol at room temperature and finally the storage condition which gave the least percentage was samples stored at room temperature.

Also, time intervals, that is the timing between sample filtration and processing in qPCR were not neglectable factors, as degradation occurred over time and clear differences in the recovery rate could be seen, for example, for *Yersinia*, a loss of eDNA of about 5% could be seen from day 3 to day 7. Moreover, the freshness and quality of the sample is of great importance. This aligns with the result, showing that on average the recovery rate of the freshly grown *Y.ruc* was 88%, while for *Aeromonas* where an old culture was taken due to contamination issues, the recovery rate was only around 72%.

During this experiment, two different methods were assessed to obtain a standard series: gBlocks and CFU standard series. And some small anomalies were detected in the Cq values, and they will be further discussed below. These results, thus, highlight the importance of optimizing the storage conditions, monitoring the sterility of all processes involved, to ensure maximum eDNA recovery.

4.2 Impact of Storage Conditions and the Mechanisms Behind

4.2.1 Dry Storage at room temperature v/s Dry at -20°C

In this research, the results have shown the undeniable effect of low temperature, specifically, -20°C here, in the maintaining and conservation of eDNA recovery and stability for both bacteria. The recovery rate at -20°C ranged between 95% to 99.6% for *Yersinia* and from 68% to 75% for *Aeromonas*. This phenomenon can be explained as follows: firstly, freezing at -20°C prevents the breakdown of eDNA by inactivating nuclease (Zai *et al.*, 2023). Secondly, the risk of contamination, hence increasing Cq value is minimized because at -20°C, metabolic reaction of unwanted microorganisms or contaminants is slowed down to almost nonexistent (Zai *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, in dry storage conditions, hydrolytic reactions which may damage DNA molecules do not take place due to the absence of moisture, which is highly present in normal storage conditions at room temperature (Howlett *et al.*, 2013). In the end, it can be noted that, for both Gram-negative bacteria, freezing at -20°C has proved to result in the best outcome for their recovery rate and this result gives insights on methods to detect low abundance of pathogens like *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* in environmental samples, where even minor losses of eDNA can significantly impact detection sensitivity.

4.2.2 Preservation with Ethanol

Preservation with Ethanol has proved to be a major asset in this research. This is due to its ability to inhibit nucleic reactions and the fact that it can also inactivate other enzymes that could cause the degradation of eDNA (Ayana *et al.*, 2019). Even A.sal samples stored in ethanol at room temperature, gave a reasonable recovery rate of on average 65% as compared to the lower recovery rate of samples stored dry at room temperature. However, a difference of around 5 to 8% % in the recovery rate of samples stored at room temperature in ethanol can be observed compared to samples stored in ethanol but at -20°C. This might be due to the fact that the protective effect of ethanol at room temperature is limited by the gradual decrease in ethanol concentration due to evaporation, which can compromise the preservation of eDNA over time (Couton *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the study also proves that the combination of ethanol and low temperature provides a dynamic and synergistic effect, resulting in the second-best storage condition, with a recovery rate of around 90 % for *Yersinia* and around 68% for *Aeromonas*. The use of ethanol at -20°C provided an additional protective layer against enzymatic degradation and

thus minimizing microbial growth that could contribute to eDNA breakdown and contamination (Ayana *et al.*, 2019).

4.2.3 Dry Storage at -20°C vs. Ethanol Storage at -20°C

Most of the results were in accordance with the expected outcome, except one storage condition which gave values lower than expected. And the storage condition is ethanol at -20°C. The expected outcome was that storage in ethanol at -20°C would be the best outcome but this experiment resulted in the samples stored dry at -20°C being the actual best outcome. This phenomenon can be explained by the fact that maybe when preparing the filtrates for extraction (after storage), there is some leftover ethanol in the filter paper, which reduces extraction success. Also some DNA, when stored, might have been washed from the filter, even though DNA is not soluble in ethanol.

Moreover, in ethanol-preserved samples, there might be the presence of moisture, thus increasing the chance of degradation due to hydrolytic reaction. And this risk is absent for the samples, stored only dry at -20°C. This complete lack of moisture in dry storage ensures that the DNA remains stable and unchanged over longer periods.

4.3 Comparative Analysis of Pathogens

Another major observation in this research is the overall difference in recovery rate of *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas*, irrespective of the storage conditions. They both had the same trend in effectiveness of the storage conditions however the recovery rate of *Yersinia* was slightly higher than that of *Aeromonas*. This confirms the hypotheses made at the beginning of the experiment concerning the importance of freshly cultivated samples and the impact that eDNA structures might have on recovery rates. *Yersinia ruckeri* samples were freshly cultured whereas the *Aeromonas salmonicida* samples were over seven months old, which likely contributed to a higher initial degradation rate for *Aeromonas salmonicida*. And secondly, *Yersinia ruckeri*, being a more robust bacterium in general (Qi *et al.*, 2016), has produced more stable eDNA compared to *Aeromonas salmonicida*.

4.4 qPCR Performance

The performance and efficiency of the qPCR assays was assessed based on their sensitivity, specificity, and consistency throughout all the qPCR runs. The assays gave positive results, demonstrating expected outcomes of high sensitivity, being able to detect low levels of eDNA with

consistent Cq values. Specificity was high for almost all samples, with minimal detection of non-targeted DNA. Reproducibility was generally good, although some variations were noted, particularly in the CFU standard series.

Performance of qPCR is normally analyzed based on their efficiency and R² value. The range for efficiency is 90 to 110 %, while R² is from 0.90 to 1.00. In this experiment, the standard curves demonstrated high R² values ranging from 0.94 to 0.99, indicating reliable quantification of eDNA. However, some anomalies were observed, particularly for *Y.ruc*, where efficiency values exceeded the typical range. These anomalies were attributed to firstly potential pipetting errors. Since a large number of samples were pipetted at once, the continuous 100% efficiency and precautions were not easy to maintain, thus there was a slight increase in errors. Moreover, contamination occurred when opening and closing the lids of tubes and the master mix during the preparation of the standard series. As shown in the results and methods part, the measured Cq values for the positive NTCs and negative would only correspond to 1-3 cell copies and according to normal qPCR guidelines provided by MIQE, (minimum information for publication of quantitative real-time PCR experiments), it is stated that the lowest concentration that can be reliably detected with a 95% confidence interval are three copies (Bustin *et al.*, 2009). Thus, in this research, the positive Cq value for the NTC and negative value can be discarded. And secondly, as mentioned above *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas* provided different results due to their respective freshness and structural properties.

Some anomalies were also observed in the Cq values and their corresponding standard series, which might be attributed to various factors. For example, some samples showed a difference in Cq values, of around 3% more for *Yersinia* and 4.2% more for *A.sal* when compared to the expected concentrations based on CFU counts. These anomalies could be due to the same pipetting errors, contamination and difficulty in maintaining the same sterile conditions for all samples.

4.5 Comparative analysis between the use of gBlocks and CFU Standard Series based on CFU

This study also provided insights on the use of gBlocks synthetic standards versus CFU standard series, standard series based on colony-forming units (CFU) for quantifying eDNA recovery. These two series cannot be exactly compared because they involve two different bacteria but a small comparison regarding their Cq value and the accuracy can be made. The gBlocks standards

provided a slightly more consistent range of Cq values by having an efficiency of 106.5% and R² of 0.941 as compared to the CFU standard series, with an efficiency of 120% and R² of 0.97.

Expected SQ	CFU standard series	gBlock series
100000000	14.01	14.08
10000000	17.85	19.21
1000000	21.02	23.55
100000	25.78	27.8
10000	27.03	32.09
1000	30.86	33.7
100	32.06	34.19
10		36.48
	Efficiency = 120 %	Efficiency = 106.5%
	R ² = 0.971	R ² = 0.941

Figure 22: The comparison between Cq values obtained from CFU standard series versus gBlocks standard series.

The use of gBlocks standards versus CFU standard series consists of both advantages and challenges. The gBlocks standards, which consist of synthetic DNA fragments with known concentrations, provide a higher precision and consistency, (Balážová *et al.*, 2020), as they are pre-manufactured and quality controlled. This precision was observed in the results obtained where the gBlocks standards produced slightly more accurate results for *Aeromonas* compared to CFU standards. The gBlocks standards minimized contamination risks and human error, which are more present in CFU-based preparations conducted within the laboratory setting.

On the other hand, CFU standard series rely on cultivating and counting live bacteria colonies (Ferdous *et al.*, 2016), introducing the probability of errors due to potential contamination during colony growth, and error when using the Nanodrop™. This study demonstrated such issues which causes higher probabilities of contamination and errors in CFU-based standard preparations. These issues can lead to inconsistencies in quantification results, as observed with *Yersinia*, where CFU-derived standards showed more fluctuation in recovery rates and Cq values compared to gBlocks-derived standards. In contrast, gBlocks standards, being synthetic and thus not affected by such biological factors, provide a more stable and reliable reference for eDNA

quantification, emphasizing their advantage in eDNA studies where precision is of great importance.

Anomalies observed when using both gBlocks and CFU standards could arise from several factors. For gBlocks standards, slight inaccuracies might be due to pipetting errors or errors in the initial DNA concentration measurements. Despite rigorous quality control, human handling has proved, in this study, to introduce minor anomalies for both *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas*.

4.6 Comparison with Existing Research

Existing research on the effects of storage conditions on eDNA recovery rates has concluded that temperature and preservative solution greatly impact eDNA integrity and detectability. This study matches the findings by Hinlo et al. (2017) and Tsuji et al. (2019), which demonstrates that lower temperatures enhance eDNA stability. Specifically, the experiment done for this thesis, confirms that storing samples at -20°C consistently yields higher recovery rates compared to room temperature storage. The range of recovery rate differences observed (10% to 20% in favor of -20°C) aligns with the research of Hinlo and Tsuji, underscoring the importance of maintaining low temperatures to minimize eDNA degradation.

Furthermore, the study's results on ethanol as a preservation solution relate to the findings by Williams et al. (2017) and Spens et al. (2017), which noted ethanol's effectiveness in preserving eDNA at lower temperatures. The high recovery rate of around 92% for *Y.ruc* and 67% for *A.sal*, achieved with ethanol preservation highlights its utility, particularly in maintaining eDNA integrity over time. However, the combination of ethanol and low temperature resulted in a slightly lower recovery rate compared to the study of William and Spens, where the combination of low temperature and ethanol resulted in the best outcome for recovery rate. As explained, this phenomenon which occurred in this experiment for the thesis might be likely due to potential eDNA dilution or degradation into the ethanol solution over time. Moreover, a study conducted by Deiner et al. (2015), where the latter reported notable eDNA degradation in samples stored at room temperature without preservatives. This study matches the results of the thesis which consisted of unpreserved samples at room temperature showing a 10% to 20% degradation rate within 24 hours. These findings highlight the critical role of timely processing and appropriate storage conditions to prevent rapid eDNA loss.

The experiment conducted here also observed anomalies in Cq values that were higher than expected when comparing filtrate DNA to standard series. This phenomenon, where Cq values

on later days were lower than those on earlier days, contradicts typical degradation expectations. Such anomalies might be attributed to filtration and handling errors, as well as inconsistencies in sample processing times. These findings echo concerns raised by Jane et al. (2015) about the potential for procedural errors impacting eDNA quantification accuracy, and the need to put more importance on rigorous protocol adherence and quality control measures in eDNA studies.

4.7 Recommendations for Future Research

This study tested several factors affecting eDNA recovery rate. However, there were some experimental and laboratory restrictions, such as a limited amount of samples to be tested and the time limit. Future research should explore a wider range of storage conditions and longer time intervals to better understand the functioning of eDNA degradation. Broadening the study to a wider range of additional pathogens relevant to aquaculture would provide a more comprehensive understanding of eDNA preservation. This study focused on only two pathogens, and the findings showed the difference between recovery rate of *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas*, by emphasizing the fact the DNA structure affects the eDNA stability. Thus, this result might not be directly applicable to other pathogens or environmental and aquatic conditions. Moreover, the investigation of longer time intervals between storage and processing in qPCR, to evaluate the degradation timelines and the effects of other preservatives could be implemented. Also exploring more advanced preservation techniques could also yield valuable insights.

Furthermore, standardizing the preparation of gBlocks and conducting field studies to validate laboratory findings in real-world conditions would also be crucial for practical applications. Finally, integrating new technologies such as digital PCR could improve the sensitivity and precision of eDNA detection and quantification and minimize the contamination and error rate.

4.8 Practical Implications for Aquaculture

The outcomes of this study have significant practical implications for the aquaculture industry. Along with existing research on the matter, more insights on the optimization of storage conditions for eDNA samples and information on efficient and reliable methods of pathogen monitoring are obtained. This leads to better disease management and control. Implementing and further analyzing the recommended storage protocols, such as freezing at -20°C and using ethanol preservation, can enhance the detection accuracy of eDNA-based assays.

These improvements in pathogen detection can contribute to healthier fish populations, reduced disease outbreaks, and increased productivity in aquaculture operations. By adopting best practices for eDNA sample storage and processing, aquaculture facilities can ensure timely and accurate identification of pathogens, supporting proactive health management strategies and sustainable aquaculture practices (Hamza *et al.*, 2023).

5. Conclusion

Nowadays, aquaculture is an essential sector and the demand for salmon is exponentially increasing. The reliability, safety of production and the salmon species are at times threatened by the outbreaks of different kinds of fish pathogens. Two of such pathogens are *Yersinia Ruckeri* and *Aeromonas salmonicida*, two gram-negative bacteria causing enteric redmouth disease (ERM) mobile *Aeromonas septicemia* (MAS), respectively. While some infections can pass unnoticed due to an asymptomatic carrier state, ongoing and recurrent outbreaks often lead to high cumulative losses. Thus, early detection is necessary, and to detect these pathogens, the method of recovering their eDNA and storing them in the optimum storage conditions for further analysis was used and tested in this research.

The aim of this study was to evaluate and test the effects of different storage conditions on the recovery rate of environmental DNA (eDNA) for both *Yersinia* and *Aeromonas*. Through experimentation involving various temperatures (room temperature which was 20 °C and also stored at -20°C), ethanol as preservation solution, and time intervals (ranging from 1 day to 14 days), this research has provided important information on the optimization of eDNA sample storage to maximize pathogen detection efficiency in aquaculture environments.

The results obtained from this study confirmed the starting hypothesis, which stated that lower temperature and Ethanol as a preservative solution and when combined with low temperature act in favor of eDNA recovery and stability. Samples stored at -20°C gave a recovery rate of around 5 to 10% more than the other storage conditions. Interestingly, one of the most unexpected results was that dry storage at -20°C gave a higher recovery rate than samples stored in ethanol at -20°C. This contradicts some existing research and assumptions and might be due to some contamination, human or pipetting errors. Thus, the trend observed from best to least efficient storage condition was: -20°C, stored in ethanol at -20°C, ethanol at room temperature and finally the one which gave the least percentage was samples stored at room temperature.

Also, the time interval between the storage and processing in the qPCR is not a neglectable factor, as degradation occurred over time and clear differences in the recovery rate could be seen. Moreover, another major observation was the difference in recovery rates between *Yersinia ruckeri* and *Aeromonas salmonicida*. *Yersinia* samples, which were freshly cultured, showed an average recovery rate of approximately 88%, whereas *Aeromonas*, from an older stock, had a lower recovery rate of about 72%. This difference demonstrates that the initial condition of the

culture can greatly impact eDNA stability and recovery, with older cultures likely to experience more substantial degradation.

Challenges, involving contamination, anomalies in the Cq values were also experienced during this study. But these challenges have helped in analyzing and building up an understanding of how much of an impact experimental protocols and sterile conditions have on obtaining the wanted results.

To conclude, this study has to be improved further and undergo more research to obtain the best practices for eDNA sample handling, which will ultimately contribute in more effective monitoring and control of fish health in natural and aquaculture environments.

6. References

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7. Statutory Declaration

I hereby declare that I wrote the present dissertation with the topic: "The Effects of Storage Conditions on the eDNA Recovery rate of Salmon Pathogens" independently and used no other aids than those cited. In each individual case, I have clearly identified the source of the passages that are taken word for word or paraphrased from other works.

I also hereby declare that I have carried out my scientific work according to the principles of good scientific practice.

Duisburg, 05.07.24

Date, Place

Signature

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9. Annex

9.1 Supplementary Data

Supplementary Table 1: List of fish pathogenic bacteria used for primer design, and their main host fish. Adapted from Sudheesh et al., 2012, Table 2, with the addition of *Vagococcus salmoninarum* from Mishra et al., 2018.

Causative Agent/Species	Disease	Main Host Fish
<i>Aeromonas salmonicida</i>	Furunculosis	Salmon, trout, goldfish, koi
<i>Flavobacterium branchiophila</i>	Bacterial gill disease	Broad range of cultured cold water and warm water salmonid and nonsalmonid fishes
<i>Flavobacterium columnare</i>	Columnaris disease	Cyprinids, salmonids, silurids, eel, sturgeon
<i>Pasteurella skyensis</i>	Pasteurellosis	Salmonids, turbot
<i>Piscirickettsia salmonis</i>	Piscirickettsiosis	Salmonids
<i>Renibacterium salmoninarum</i>	Bacterial kidney disease	Salmonids
<i>Streptococcus phocae</i>	Streptococcosis	Atlantic salmon
<i>Vagococcus salmoninarum</i>	Vagococcosis	Rainbow trout, atlantic salmon, brown trout
<i>Vibrio anguillarum</i>	Vibriosis	Salmonids, turbot, sea bass, striped bass, eel, ayu, cod, red sea bream
<i>Yersinia ruckeri</i>	Enteric redmouth	Salmonids, eel, minnows, sturgeon, crustaceans

Table 16: Reference table when building PCR program.

Step	(°C)	Time	Cycles	Notes
Initial Denaturation	95	3 min	1	
Denaturation	95	30 sec	30-35	
Annealing - glnA	55-60	30 sec	30-35	Temperature depends on the primer T _m
Annealing - VapA	55-60	30 sec	30-35	Temperature depends on the primer T _m
Annealing - 16S rRNA	50-55	30 sec	30-35	Temperature depends on the primer T _m
Extension	72	1 min per kb	30-35	Adjust time based on amplicon length
Final Extension	72	5-10 min	1	
Hold	4	Indefinite	1	

9.2 Devices used

- qPCR: Bio-Rad CFX96 Touch™ Real-Time PCR Detection System
- PCR: SensoQuest Labcycler Gradient (Thermoblock 96 wells)
- Centrifuge: Select BioProducts SelectSpin™ 21 Ambient Microcentrifuge
- Photometer: Tecan Sunrise absorbance microplate reader
- Thermomixer. Eppendorf Thermomixer compact
- Incubator: VWR® Incubating Orbital Shaker, Model 35001
- Nanodrop. Thermo Scientific™ NanoDrop™™ One
- Other devices Vortex, UV table, Incubator Oven

9.3 Software used

- CFX Maestro™ Software Version 2.2
- Unipro UGENE Version 38.1 (64-bit)- March 2021

- MathWorks Matlab R2020b Update 5 (64-bit)-Feb 2021
- Microsoft Excel
- XFluor4 Version 4.51